

Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 8 to 108

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Abstract

*This paper brings idea how we can organize **block-wise** constructions of magic and **bimagic** squares. This we have done for the magic squares of orders 8 to 108. By use of the formula for the calculations of magic squares, we can check the existence of blocks of equal or unequal sums. In case of blocks of order 3, either we have equal sums of semi-magic blocks or unequal blocks of magic squares of order 3. While, in case of blocks of order 4, 5 and 7, the magic squares can be written as **pandiagonal**. For the case of blocks of order 6, the blocks are of equal magic sums, but the magic squares are not **pandiagonal**.*

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1 Introduction

In this work we brought **block-wise** constructions of magic squares for the orders 8 to 108 with possible existence of blocks. Let’s divide the natural numbers from 8 to 108 in three groups.

1.1 Groups

The natural numbers from 8 to 108 are divided three groups. See below:

- i. **Prime numbers:** 11, 13, 17, 19, 23, 29, 31, 37, 41, 43, 47, 53, 59, 61, 67, 71, 73, 79, 83, 89, 97, 101, 103 and 107. In this case, the constructions are simple. Knowing one, we can construct other on similar lines. Moreover, the prime order magic squares can be constructed always **pandiagonal**. Also the prime order magic square are helpful in constructing **block-wise** magic squares given in item (iii). It is used for the multiples of 3 and more. For example, 33, 39, 44, etc.
- ii. **Double of prime numbers:** 10, 14, 22, 26, 34, 38, 46, 58, 62, 74, 82, 86, 94 and 106. In this case, there is no unique procedure to construct these magic squares. Generally, the constructions are based on **pair of mutually orthogonal diagonal Latin squares** or on **self-orthogonal diagonal Latin squares**. In this case, the reader can use the software produced by W. Harry [3]. Since all these magic squares are of type $4k + 2, k > 1$, they will never be **pandiagonal**. Recently, W. Harry [4] produced another software, where the bordered constructions can be made for the items given in (i) and (ii), where internal blocks are of equal magic square sums. Still, there are more magic squares of type $4k + 2, k > 1$, not double of prime numbers, for example, 30, 42, 54, 66, etc. are under study appearing in item (iii).
- iii. **Block-wise Orders:** 8, 9, 12, 15, 16, 18, 20, 21, 24, 25, 27, 28, 30, 32, 33, 35, 36, 39, 40, 42, 44, 45, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 54, 55, 56, 57, 60, 63, 64, 65, 66, 68, 69, 70, 72, 75, 76, 77, 78, 80, 81, 84, 85, 87, 88, 90, 91, 92, 93, 95, 96, 98, 99, 100, 102, 104, 105 and 108. In this case, the details are given Section 2.

This work is concentrated on magic squares given in item (iii). The explanations are given in such a way that readers are not necessary to use any programming language to construct them. In each case, all the possibilities are considered. It depends on the magic square sums divisions, leading us to equal or unequal magic square sum blocks. After analysing, the results are summarized in following theorem.

1.2 Main Theorem

The following Theorem resumes the Results analysed in Section 2 on the **block-wise** construction of magic squares.

Theorem 1.1. *The block-wise constructions of magic squares are given by*

i. **Blocks of Order 3:** *It is always possible to construct magic squares of orders:*

- (a) $(2k + 1) \times 3, k \geq 1, k \in \mathbf{N}$, with blocks of equal sums **semi-magic** squares (rows and columns) of order 3, for example, magic squares of orders: 9, 15, 21, 27, ... In this case the magic squares are **pandiagonal**.
- (b) $2k \times 3, k \geq 2, k \in \mathbf{N}$, with blocks of **different magic square sums** of order 3, for example, magic squares of orders: 12, 18, 24, 30, ... In this case, not all the magic squares are **pandiagonal**.

ii. **Blocks of Order 4:** *It is always possible to construct **pandiagonal** magic squares of orders $4k, k \geq 2, k \in \mathbf{N}$, with blocks of **pandiagonal equal magic square sums** of order 4, for example, magic squares of orders: 8, 12, 16, 20, ...;*

iii. **Blocks of Order 5:** It is always possible to construct magic squares of orders

- (a) $(2k + 1) \times 5, k \geq 1, k \in \mathbf{N}$, with blocks of **pandiagonal equal magic square sums** of order 5, for example, magic squares of orders: 15, 25, 35, 45, ... In this case, the magic squares are **pandiagonal**.
- (b) $2k \times 5, k \geq 2, k \in \mathbf{N}$, with blocks of **pandiagonal different magic square sums** of order 5, for example, magic squares of orders: 20, 30, 40, 50, ... In this case, not all the magic squares are **pandiagonal**.

iv. **Blocks of Order 6:** It is always possible to construct magic squares of orders $6k, k \geq 2, k \in \mathbf{N}$, with blocks of equal sums magic squares of order 6, for example, magic squares of orders: 12, 18, 24, 30, ...;

v. **Blocks of Order 7:** It is always possible to construct magic squares of orders

- (a) $(2k + 1) \times 7, k \geq 1, k \in \mathbf{N}$, with blocks of **pandiagonal equal magic square sums** of order 7, for example, magic squares of orders: 21, 35, 49, 63, ... In this case, the magic squares are **pandiagonal**.
- (b) $2k \times 7, k \geq 2, k \in \mathbf{N}$, with blocks of **pandiagonal different magic square sums** of order 7, for example, magic squares of orders: 28, 42, 56, 70, 84, 98, ... In this case, not all the magic squares are **pandiagonal**.

vi. **Blocks of Prime Numbers Higher Than 7:** It is always possible to construct

- (a) **pandiagonal** magic squares of orders $mp, m \geq 3, p \geq 11, m \in \mathbf{N}, p = \text{prime number}$, with blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order p , for example, $m = 3, 4, 5, \dots$ and $p = 11, 13, 17, 19, \dots$;
- (b) magic squares of order $2mp, m \geq 2, p \geq 5, m \in \mathbf{N}, p = \text{prime number}$ with blocks of magic squares of order $2p$, for example, $m = 2, 3, 4, \dots$; and $p = 5, 7, 11, 13, \dots$, or $2p = 10, 14, 22, 26, \dots$. The magic square orders are of type, 20, 40, 28, 44, 52, 60, etc.;

vii. **Blocks of Orders 8, 9, 12, 15, 16, etc.** These blocks are not written here as they may vary according to choices, for example, **bimagic, semi-bimagic, pandiagonal, etc.**

2 Block-Wise Construction of Magic Squares

To start with we need a general formula of magic sum of order n , i.e., the magic sum of order n of consecutive numbers from 1 to n^2 is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n \times (1 + n^2)}{2}, n \geq 3.$$

Let's analyse each case separately.

2.1 Magic Squares of order 8

The magic sum of order 8 is given by

$$S_{8 \times 8} := \frac{8 \times (1 + 8^2)}{2} = 260.$$

We can write, $8 := 2^3 = 2 \times 2 \times 2$. This gives the possibility of blocks of order 4. In order to get blocks of order 4, we have to divide the total magic sum 260 by 2. Let's see this division:

$$\frac{260}{2} = 130 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 4.}$$

Result 1. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 8 is given by*

- i. 4 Blocks of Order 4: The pandigonal magic square of order 8 is constructed with 4 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 4*
- ii. Bimagic Square of Order 8: The construction of bimagic square of order 8 is well known in the history, and is done by G. Pfeffermann. 1891. In this case, we have a pandiagonal bimagic square of order 8, where the blocks of order 2×4 are of same sum.*

2.2 Magic Squares of order 9

The magic sum of order 9 is given by

$$S_{9 \times 9} := \frac{9 \times (1 + 9^2)}{2} = 369.$$

We can write, $9 := 3^2 = 3 \times 3$. This gives the possibility of blocks of order 3. Let's see the division of magic square sum 369 by 3:

$$\frac{369}{3} = 123 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 3.}$$

Result 2. *The block-wise construction magic of square of order 9 is given by*

- i. 9 Blocks of Order 3: The pandigonal magic square of order 9 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal semi-magic sums (rows and columns) of order 3;*
- ii. Bimagic Square of Order 9: The bimagic square construction is well known in the history by G. Pfeffermann in 1891. In this case, block sums of order 3 are the same.*

2.3 Magic Squares of order 12

The magic sum of order 12 is given by

$$S_{12 \times 12} := \frac{12 \times (1 + 12^2)}{2} = 870.$$

We can write, $12 := 2^2 \times 3 = 2 \times 2 \times 3$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 4 and 6. In order to get blocks of orders 3, 4 and 6, we have to divide the magic square sum 870 by 4, 3 and 2. Let's see these divisions:

- (i) $\frac{870}{4} = 217.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{870}{3} = 290 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (ii) $\frac{870}{2} = 435 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6.

Result 3. The *block-wise construction of magic square of order 12 is given by*

- i. **12 Blocks of Order 3:** The *pandigonal* magic square of order 12 is constructed with 12 blocks of different magic squares sums of order 3. Magic sums of order 3 again lead us to a *pandigonal* magic square of order 4;
- ii. **9 Blocks of Order 4:** The *pandigonal* magic square of order 12 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal magic square sums of order 4;
- iii. **4 Blocks of Order 6:** The magic square of order 12 is constructed with 4 blocks of equal magic square sums of order 6.

2.4 Magic Squares of order 15

The magic sum of order 15 is given by

$$S_{15 \times 15} := \frac{15 \times (1 + 15^2)}{2} = 1695.$$

We can write, $15 := 3 \times 5$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3 and 5. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 1695 by 5 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{1595}{5} = 339 \implies$ equal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{29679}{3} = 565 \implies$ equal blocks of order 5.

Result 4. The *block-wise construction of magic square of order 15 is given by*

- i. **25 Blocks of Order 3:** The *pandigonal* magic square of order 15 is constructed with 25 blocks of equal *semi-magic* square sums (rows and columns) of order 3;
- ii. **9 Blocks of Order 5:** The *pandigonal* magic square of order 15 is constructed with 9 blocks of *pandiagonal* magic squares of equal magic sums of order 5.

2.5 Magic Squares of order 16

The magic sum of order 16 is given by

$$S_{16 \times 16} := \frac{16 \times (1 + 16^2)}{2} = 2056.$$

We can write, $16 := 4^2 = 4 \times 4$. This gives the possibility of blocks of order 4 and 8. Let's see division of 2056 by 4 and 2:

$$(i) \quad \frac{2056}{4} = 514 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 4;}$$
$$(ii) \quad \frac{2056}{2} = 1028 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 8.}$$

Result 5. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 16 is given by*

- i. 16 Blocks of order 4: The pandiagonal magic square of order 16 is constructed with 16 blocks of pandiagonal magic squares of equal magic sums of order 4.*
- ii. 16 Blocks of order 4: Bimagic - The bimagic square of order 16 is constructed with 16 blocks of equal magic squares sums of order 4.*

2.6 Magic Squares of order 18

The magic sum of order 18 is given by

$$S_{18 \times 18} := \frac{18 \times (1 + 18^2)}{2} = 2925.$$

We can write, $18 := 2 \times 3 \times 3$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3 and 6. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 2925 by 6 and 3:

$$(i) \quad \frac{2925}{6} = 487.5 \implies \text{unequal blocks of order 3;}$$
$$(ii) \quad \frac{2925}{3} = 975 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 6.}$$

Result 6. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 18 is given by*

- i. 36 Blocks of order 3: The magic square of order 18 is constructed with 36 blocks of different magic square sums of order 3. Magic square sums of order 3, again lead us to a magic square of order 6;*
- ii. 9 Blocks of order 6: The magic square of order 18 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal magic squares sums of order 6*

In this case, we don't have any pandiagonal magic square of order 18.

2.7 Magic Squares of order 20

The magic sum of order 20 is given by

$$S_{20 \times 20} := \frac{20 \times (1 + 20^2)}{2} = 4010.$$

We can write, $20 := 2 \times 2 \times 5$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4, 5 and 10. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 4010 by 5, 4 and 2:

- (i) $\frac{4010}{5} = 802 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (ii) $\frac{4010}{4} = 1002.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 5;
- (iii) $\frac{4010}{2} = 2005 \implies$ equal blocks of order 10.

Result 7. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 20 is given by*

- i. **25 Blocks of Order 4:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 20 is constructed with equal pandiagonal magic squares sums of order 4.*
- ii. **16 Blocks of Order 5:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 20 is constructed with different magic sums of pandiagonal magic squares of order 5. The 16 magic squares of order 5, lead us to a pandiagonal magic square of order 4;*
- iii. **4 Blocks of Order 10:** *The magic square of order 20 is constructed with equal sums magic squares of order 10.*

2.8 Magic Squares of order 21

The magic sum of order 21 is given by

$$S_{21 \times 21} := \frac{21 \times (1 + 21^2)}{2} = 4641.$$

We can write, $21 := 3 \times 7$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3 and 7. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 4641 by 7 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{4641}{7} = 663 \implies$ equal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{4641}{3} = 1547 \implies$ equal blocks of order 7.

Result 8. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 21 is given by*

- i. **49 Blocks of Order 3:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 21 is constructed with 49 blocks of equal semi-magic square sums (rows and columns) of order 3;*
- ii. **9 Blocks of Order 7:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 21 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 7.*

2.9 Magic Squares of order 24

The magic sum of order 24 is given by

$$S_{24 \times 24} := \frac{24 \times (1 + 24^2)}{2} = 6924.$$

We can write, $24 := 2^3 \times 3 = 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 3$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 4, 6, 8 and 12. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 6924 by 8, 6, 4, 3 and 2:

- (i) $\frac{6924}{8} = 865.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{6924}{6} = 1154 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (iii) $\frac{6924}{4} = 1731 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6;
- (iv) $\frac{6924}{3} = 2308 \implies$ equal blocks of order 8;
- (v) $\frac{6924}{2} = 3462 \implies$ equal blocks of order 12.

Result 9. The *block-wise* construction of magic square of order 24 is given by

- i. **64 Blocks of Order 3:** The *pandigonal* magic square of order 24 is constructed with 64 blocks of different magic sums of magic squares of order 3. Also 64 magic sums of order 3 results in a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 8;
- ii. **36 Blocks of Order 4:** The *pandigonal* magic square of order 24 is constructed with 36 blocks of equal sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 4;
- iii. **16 Blocks of Order 6:** The magic square of order 24 is constructed with 16 blocks of equal magic squares sums of order 6;
- iv. **9 Blocks of Order 8: Semi-Bimagic** The *semi-bimagic* square of order 24 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 8. Blocks of order 8 are either *bimagic* or *semi-bimagic* squares;
- v. **4 Blocks of Order 12:** The magic squares of order 12 are constructed according to Result 3. This possibility comes under the first or second case described above, i.e., 4 blocks of order 12 with equal magic square sums lead us to a magic square of order 24.

2.10 Magic Squares of order 25

The magic sum of order 25 is given by

$$S_{25 \times 25} := \frac{25 \times (1 + 25^2)}{2} = 7825.$$

We can write, $25 := 5^2 = 5 \times 5$. This gives the possibility of blocks of order 5. This sum is divisible by 5. See below:

$$\frac{7825}{5} = 1565 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 5.}$$

Result 10. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order is given by*

- i. 25 blocks of order 5: Bimagic - In this case, pandigonal bimagic magic square of order 25 is constructed with 25 blocks of pandiagonal equal magic sums of order 5;*

2.11 Magic Squares of order 27

The magic sum of order 27 is given by

$$S_{27 \times 27} := \frac{27 \times (1 + 27^2)}{2} = 9855.$$

We can write, $27 := 3^3 = 3 \times 3 \times 3$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3 and 9. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 9855 by 9 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{9855}{9} = 1095 \implies$ equal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{9855}{3} = 3285 \implies$ equal blocks of order 9.

Result 11. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 27 is given by*

- i. 81 Blocks of Order 3: The pandigonal magic square of order 27 is constructed with 81 blocks of equal semi-magic square sums (rows and columns) of order 3;*
- ii. 9 Blocks of Order 9: The pandigonal magic square of order 27 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic square of order 9.*

2.12 Magic Squares of order 28

The magic sum of order 28 is given by

$$S_{28 \times 28} := \frac{28 \times (1 + 28^2)}{2} = 10990.$$

We can write, $28 := 2^2 \times 7 = 2 \times 2 \times 7$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4, 7 and 14. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 10990 by 7, 4 and 2:

- (i) $\frac{10990}{7} = 1570 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (ii) $\frac{10990}{4} = 2747.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 7;
- (iii) $\frac{10990}{2} = 5495 \implies$ equal blocks of order 14.

Result 12. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 28 is given by*

- i. 49 Blocks of Order 4: The pandigonal magic square of order 28 is constructed with 49 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 4.*

- ii. **16 Blocks of Order 7:** The *pandigonal* magic square of order 28 is constructed with 16 blocks of different magic sums of *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 7. Also, magic sums of order 7 results in a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 4.
- iii. **4 Blocks of Order 14:** The magic square of order 28 is constructed with 4 blocks of equal sums magic squares of order 14.

2.13 Magic Squares of order 30

The magic sum of order 30 is given by

$$S_{30 \times 30} := \frac{30 \times (1 + 30^2)}{2} = 13515.$$

We can write, $30 := 2 \times 3 \times 5$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 5, 6 and 10. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 13515 by 10, 6, 5 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{13515}{10} = 1351.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{13515}{6} = 2252.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 5;
- (i) $\frac{13515}{5} = 2703 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6;
- (ii) $\frac{13515}{3} = 4505 \implies$ equal blocks of order 10.

Result 13. The *block-wise* construction of magic square of order 30 is given by

- i. **100 Blocks of Order 3:** The magic square of order 30 is constructed with 100 blocks of different magic sums of magic squares of order 3. Also 100 magic sums of order 3 results in a magic square of order 10;
- ii. **36 Blocks of Order 5:** The magic square of order 30 is constructed with 36 blocks of different magic sums of *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 5;
- iii. **25 Blocks of Order 6:** The magic square of order 30 is constructed with 25 blocks of equal sum magic squares of order 6;
- iv. **9 Blocks of Order 10:** The magic square of order 30 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal sum magic squares of order 10;

In this case, we don't have any *pandiagonal* magic square of order 30.

2.14 Magic Squares of order 32

The magic sum of order 32 is given by

$$S_{32 \times 32} := \frac{32 \times (1 + 32^2)}{2} = 16400.$$

We can write, $32 := 2^5 = 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4 and 8. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 16400 by 8 and 4:

$$(i) \quad \frac{16400}{8} = 2050 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 4;}$$

$$(ii) \quad \frac{16400}{4} = 4100 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 8.}$$

Result 14. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 32 is given by*

- i. 64 Blocks of Order 4: The pandigonal magic square of order 32 is constructed with 64 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 4.*
- ii. 16 Blocks of Order 8: Bimagic - The pandiagonal bimagic square of order 32 is constructed with 16 blocks of different magic sums of semi-bimagic squares of order 8. The 16 magic sums of semi-bimagic squares of order 8 again lead us to a pandiagonal magic square of order 4.*

2.15 Magic Squares of order 33

The magic sum of order 33 is given by

$$S_{33 \times 33} := \frac{33 \times (1 + 33^2)}{2} = 17985.$$

We can write, $33 := 3 \times 11$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3 and 11. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 17985 by 11 and 3:

$$(i) \quad \frac{17985}{11} = 1635 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 3;}$$

$$(ii) \quad \frac{17985}{3} = 5995 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 11.}$$

Result 15. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 33 is given by*

- i. 121 Blocks of Order 3: The pandigonal magic square of order 33 is constructed with 121 blocks of equal semi-magic square sums (rows and columns) of order 3;*
- ii. 9 Blocks of Order 11: The pandigonal magic square of order 33 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 11.*

2.16 Magic Squares of order 35

The magic sum of order 35 is given by

$$S_{35 \times 35} := \frac{35 \times (1 + 35^2)}{2} = 21455.$$

We can write, $35 := 5 \times 7$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 5 and 7. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 21455 by 7 and 5:

$$(i) \quad \frac{21455}{7} = 3065 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 5;}$$

$$(ii) \quad \frac{21455}{5} = 4291 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 7.}$$

Result 16. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 35 is given by*

- i. 49 Blocks of Order 5: The pandigonal magic square of order 35 is constructed with equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 7;*
- ii. 25 Blocks of Order 7: The pandigonal magic square of order 35 is constructed with equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 5.*

2.17 Magic Squares of order 36

The magic sum of order 36 is given by

$$S_{36 \times 36} := \frac{36 \times (1 + 36^2)}{2} = 23346.$$

We can write, $36 := 2^2 \times 3^2 = 2 \times 2 \times 3 \times 3$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 4, 6, 9 and 12. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 23346 by 12, 9, 6, 4 and 3:

$$(i) \quad \frac{23346}{12} = 1945.5 \implies \text{unequal blocks of order 3;}$$

$$(ii) \quad \frac{23346}{9} = 2594 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 4;}$$

$$(iii) \quad \frac{23346}{6} = 3891 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 6;}$$

$$(iii) \quad \frac{23346}{4} = 5836.5 \implies \text{unequal blocks of order 9;}$$

$$(iv) \quad \frac{23346}{3} = 7782 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 12.}$$

Result 17. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 36 is given by*

- i. 144 Blocks of Order 3: The pandigonal magic square of order 36 is constructed with 144 blocks of different magic sums of magic squares of order 3. Also 144 magic sums of order 3 results in a pandiagonal magic square of order 12;*
- ii. 81 Blocks of Order 4: The pandigonal magic square of order 36 is constructed with 81 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 4;*
- iii. 36 Blocks of Order 6: The magic square of order 36 is constructed with 36 blocks of equal magic squares sums of order 6;*

- iv. **16 Blocks of Order 9:** The *pandigonal* magic square of order 36 is constructed with 16 blocks of different *pandiagonal* magic squares sums of order 9. Also 16 magic sums of order 9 results in a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 4;
- v. **9 Blocks of Order 12:** The *pandigonal* magic square of order 36 is constructed with 9 blocks of *pandiagonal* magic squares equal magic sums of order 12. The magic squares of order 12 are constructed according to part (i) of Result 3, i.e., different magic square sums of order 3.

Remark 2.1. There is another construction of *pandiagonal bimagic* square of order 36, where blocks of order 6 are of equal block sums as of magic square, i.e., $S_{36} \times 36 := 23346$. The magic square is done by... and is available at C. Boyer's site.

2.18 Magic Squares of order 39

The magic sum of order 39 is given by

$$S_{39 \times 39} := \frac{39 \times (1 + 39^2)}{2} = 29679.$$

We can write, $39 := 3 \times 13$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3 and 13. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 29679 by 13 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{29679}{13} = 2293 \implies$ equal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{29679}{3} = 9893 \implies$ equal blocks of order 13.

Result 18. The *block-wise* construction of magic square of order 39 is given by

- i. **169 Blocks of Order 3:** The *pandigonal* magic square of order 39 is constructed with 169 blocks of equal *semi-magic* square sums (rows and columns) of order 3;
- ii. **9 Blocks of Order 13:** The *pandigonal* magic square of order 39 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 13.

2.19 Magic Squares of order 40

The magic sum of order 40 is given by

$$S_{40 \times 40} := \frac{40 \times (1 + 40^2)}{2} = 32020.$$

We can write, $40 := 2^3 \times 5 = 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 5$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4, 5, 8 and 10. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 32020 by 10, 8, 5 and 4:

- (i) $\frac{32020}{10} = 3202 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (ii) $\frac{32020}{8} = 4002.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 5;
- (iii) $\frac{32020}{5} = 6404 \implies$ equal blocks of order 8;
- (iv) $\frac{32020}{4} = 8005 \implies$ equal blocks of order 10.

Result 19. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 40 is given by*

- i. 100 Blocks of Order 4: The pandigonal magic square of order 40 is constructed with 100 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 4;*
- ii. 64 Blocks of Order 5: The pandigonal magic square of order 40 is constructed with 64 blocks of different pandiagonal magic squares sums of order 5;*
- iii. 25 Blocks of Order 8: Bimagic - The pandigonal bimagic magic square of order 40 is constructed with 25 blocks of semi-bimagic pandiagonal magic squares of order 8;*
- iv. 16 Blocks of Order 10: The magic square of order 40 is constructed with 16 blocks of equal magic square sums of order 10.*

2.20 Magic Squares of order 42

The magic sum of order 42 is given by

$$S_{42 \times 42} := \frac{42 \times (1 + 42^2)}{2} = 37065.$$

We can write, $42 := 2 \times 3 \times 7$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 6, 7 and 14. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 37065 by 14, 7, 6 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{37065}{14} = 2647.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{37065}{7} = 5295 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6;
- (iii) $\frac{37065}{6} = 6176.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 7;
- (iv) $\frac{37065}{3} = 12355 \implies$ equal blocks of order 14.

Result 20. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 42 is given by*

- i. 196 Blocks of Order 3: The magic square of order 42 is constructed with 196 blocks of different magic squares sums of order 3. Also 196 magic sums of order 3 results in a magic square of order 14;*
- ii. 49 Blocks of Order 6: The magic square of order 42 is constructed with 49 blocks of equal magic square sums of order 6.*
- iii. 36 Blocks of Order 7: The magic square of order 42 is constructed with 36 blocks of different pandiagonal magic square sums of order 7.*
- iv. 9 Blocks of Order 14: The magic square of order 42 is constructed with 9 blocks of equal magic square sums of order 14.*

In this case, we don't have any pandiagonal magic square of order 42.

2.21 Magic Squares of order 44

The magic sum of order 44 is given by

$$S_{44 \times 44} := \frac{44 \times (1 + 44^2)}{2} = 42614.$$

We can write, $44 := 2^2 \times 4 = 2 \times 2 \times 11$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4, 11 and 22. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 42614 by 11, 4 and 2:

- (i) $\frac{42614}{11} = 3874 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (ii) $\frac{42614}{4} = 10653.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 11;
- (ii) $\frac{42614}{2} = 21307 \implies$ equal blocks of order 22.

Result 21. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 44 is given by*

- i. **121 Blocks of Order 4:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 44 is constructed with 121 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 4;*
- ii. **16 Blocks of Order 11:** *The pandigonal magic square of order 44 is constructed with 16 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 11;*
- iii. **4 Blocks of Order 22:** *The magic square of order 44 is constructed with 4 blocks of equal magic square sums of order 22;*

2.22 Magic Squares of order 45

The magic sum of order 45 is given by

$$S_{45 \times 45} := \frac{45 \times (1 + 45^2)}{2} = 45585.$$

We can write, $45 := 3^2 \times 5 = 3 \times 3 \times 5$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 5, 9 and 15. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 45585 by 15, 9, 5 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{45585}{15} = 3039 \implies$ equal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{45585}{9} = 5065 \implies$ equal blocks of order 5;
- (iii) $\frac{45585}{5} = 9117 \implies$ equal blocks of order 9;
- (iv) $\frac{45585}{3} = 15195 \implies$ equal blocks of order 15.

Result 22. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 45 is given by*

- i. **225 Blocks of Order 3:** The **pandigonal** magic square of order 45 is constructed with 225 blocks of equal **semi-magic** square sums (rows and columns) of order 3;
- ii. **81 Blocks of Order 5:** In this case, **pandigonal** magic squares of order 5 with equal magic sums results in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 45;
- iii. **25 Blocks of Order 9:** In this case we can have **pandiagonal** magic square of order 45 with equal magic sums of order 9. If we want magic square of order 9 also **pandiagonal**, in this case, the blocks of order 9 are with different magic sums.
- iv. **9 Blocks of Order 15:** This case is already included in the **block-wise** construction of equal magic sums of **pandigonal** magic squares of order 5.

2.23 Magic Squares of order 48

The magic sum of order 48 is given by

$$S_{48 \times 48} := \frac{48 \times (1 + 48^2)}{2} = 55320.$$

We can write, $48 := 2^4 \times 3 = 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 3$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 4, 6, 8, 12 and 16. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 55320 by 16, 12, 8, 6, 4 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{55320}{16} = 3457.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{55320}{12} = 4610 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (iii) $\frac{55320}{8} = 6915 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6;
- (iv) $\frac{55320}{6} = 9220 \implies$ equal blocks of order 8;
- (v) $\frac{55320}{4} = 13840 \implies$ equal blocks of order 12;
- (vi) $\frac{55320}{3} = 18440 \implies$ equal blocks of order 16.

Result 23. The **block-wise** construction of magic square of order 48 is given by

- i. **256 Blocks of Order 3:** The magic square of order 48 is constructed with 256 blocks of different magic squares sums of order 3. Also 256 magic sums of order 3 results in a magic square of order 16;
- ii. **144 Blocks of Order 4:** The **pandigonal** magic square of order 48 is constructed with 144 blocks of equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4;
- iii. **64 Blocks of Order 6:** The magic square of order 48 is constructed with 64 blocks of equal magic squares sums of order 6;
- iv. **36 Blocks of Order 8:** This possibility is already included in the previous case with blocks of order 4. Even if we use **bimagic** or **semi-bimagic** squares of order 8, still we get a magic square of order 48;

- v. **16 Blocks of Order 12:** The *pandigonal* magic square of order 48 is constructed with 16 blocks of equal sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 12. The *pandigonal* magic square of order 12 is constructed according to Result 3 part (i), i.e., with different magic square sums of order 3;
- vi. **9 Blocks of Order 16: Semi-Bimagic** - In this case we have a *semi-bimagic* square of order 48, where each block of order 16 a *bimagic square* with equal magic sums constructed according to Result 5 part (ii). Blocks of order 4 are of equal magic sums.

2.24 Magic Squares of order 49

The magic sum of order 49 is given by

$$S_{49 \times 49} := \frac{49 \times (1 + 49^2)}{2} = 58849.$$

We can write, $49 := 7^2 = 7 \times 7$. This gives the possibility of blocks of order 7. Let's see division of 58849 by 7:

$$\frac{58849}{7} = 8407 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 7.}$$

Result 24. The *block-wise* construction of magic square of order 49 is given by

- i. **49 Blocks of Order 7: Bimagic Square of Order 49** - The *pandiagonal bimagic* square of order 49 is constructed with *pandiagonal* equal magic sums of order 7.

2.25 Magic Squares of order 50

The magic sum of order 50 is given by

$$S_{50 \times 50} := \frac{50 \times (1 + 50^2)}{2} = 62525.$$

We can write, $50 := 2 \times 5^2 = 2 \times 5 \times 5$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 5 and 10. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 62525 by 10 and 5:

- (i) $\frac{45585}{10} = 6265.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 5;
- (ii) $\frac{45585}{5} = 12505 \implies$ equal blocks of order 10.

Result 25. The *block-wise* construction of magic square of order 50 is given by

- i. **100 Blocks of Order 5:** The magic square of order 50 is constructed with 100 blocks of different *pandiagonal* magic square sums of order 5. Also, magic sums of order 5 lead us to a magic square of order 10. In this case, the magic square of order 50 is not *pandiagonal*.
- ii. **25 Blocks of Order 10:** The magic square of order 50 is constructed with 25 blocks of equal sums magic squares of order 10.

2.26 Magic Squares of order 51

The magic sum of order 51 is given by

$$S_{51 \times 51} := \frac{51 \times (1 + 51^2)}{2} = 66351.$$

We can write, $51 := 3 \times 17$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3 and 17. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 66351 by 17 and 3:

$$(i) \quad \frac{66351}{17} = 3903 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 3;}$$

$$(ii) \quad \frac{66351}{3} = 22117 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 17;}$$

Result 26. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 51 is given by*

- i. 289 Blocks of Order 3: The pandigonal magic square of order 51 is constructed with 289 blocks of equal semi-magic square sums (rows and columns) of order 3;*
- ii. 9 Blocks of Order 17: The pandigonal magic square of order 51 is constructed with 9 blocks of pandigonal equal sums magic squares of order 17.*

2.27 Magic Squares of order 52

The magic sum of order 52 is given by

$$S_{52 \times 52} := \frac{52 \times (1 + 52^2)}{2} = 70330.$$

We can write, $52 := 2^2 \times 13 = 2 \times 2 \times 13$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4 and 13. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 70330 by 13 and 4:

$$(i) \quad \frac{45585}{13} = 5410 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 4;}$$

$$(ii) \quad \frac{45585}{4} = 17582.5 \implies \text{unequal blocks of order 13.}$$

Result 27. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 52 is given by*

- i. 169 Blocks of Order 4: The pandigonal magic square of order 52 is constructed with 169 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 4;*
- ii. 16 Blocks of Order 13: The pandigonal magic square of order 52 is constructed with 16 blocks of equal sums pandiagonal magic squares of order 13;*

2.28 Magic Squares of order 54

The magic sum of order 54 is given by

$$S_{54 \times 54} := \frac{54 \times (1 + 54^2)}{2} = 78759.$$

We can write, $54 := 2 \times 3^3 = 2 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 6, 9 and 18. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 78759 by 18, 9, 6 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{78759}{18} = 4375.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{78759}{9} = 8751 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6;
- (iii) $\frac{78759}{6} = 13126.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 9;
- (iv) $\frac{78759}{3} = 26253 \implies$ equal blocks of order 18.

Result 28. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 54 is given by*

- i. 324 Blocks of Order 3: Unequal magic square sums of order 3;*
 - ii. 81 Blocks of Order 6: Equal magic square sums of order 6;*
 - iii. 36 Blocks of Order 9: Unequal magic square sums of order 9;*
 - iv. 9 Blocks of Order 18: Equal magic square sums of order 18;*
- In this case, we don't have any pandiagonal magic square of order 54.*

2.29 Magic Squares of order 55

The magic sum of order 55 is given by

$$S_{55 \times 55} := \frac{55 \times (1 + 55^2)}{2} = 83215.$$

We can write, $55 := 5 \times 11$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 5 and 11. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 83215 by 11 and 5:

- (i) $\frac{83215}{11} = 7565 \implies$ equal blocks of order 5;
- (ii) $\frac{83215}{5} = 16643 \implies$ equal blocks of order 11.

Result 29. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 55 is given by*

- i. 121 Blocks of Order 5: In this case, pandiagonal magic squares of order 5 with equal magic sums results in a pandiagonal magic square of order 55;*
- ii. 25 Blocks of Order 11: In this case, pandiagonal magic squares of order 11 with equal magic sums results in a pandiagonal magic square of order 55.*

2.30 Magic Squares of order 56

The magic sum of order 56 is given by

$$S_{56 \times 56} := \frac{56 \times (1 + 56^2)}{2} = 87836.$$

We can write, $56 := 2^3 \times 7 = 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 7$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4, 7, 8 and 14. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 87836 by 14, 8, 7 and 4:

- (i) $\frac{87836}{14} = 6274 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (ii) $\frac{87836}{8} = 10979.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 7;
- (iii) $\frac{87836}{7} = 12548 \implies$ equal blocks of order 8;
- (iv) $\frac{87836}{4} = 21959 \implies$ equal blocks of order 14.

Result 30. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 56 is given by*

- i. **196 Blocks of Order 4:** *In this case, pandigonal magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums results in a pandiagonal magic square of order 56;*
- ii. **64 Blocks of Order 7:** *Unequal magic square sums of order 7;*
- iii. **49 Blocks of Order 8: Bimagic -** *Equal magic square sums of order 8;*
- iv. **16 Blocks of Order 14:** *Equal magic square sums of order 14.*

2.31 Magic Squares of order 57

The magic sum of order 57 is given by

$$S_{57 \times 57} := \frac{57 \times (1 + 57^2)}{2} = 92625.$$

We can write, $57 := 3 \times 19$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, and 19. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 92625 by 19 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{92625}{19} = 4875 \implies$ equal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{92625}{3} = 30875 \implies$ equal blocks of order 19.

Result 31. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 57 is given by*

- i. **361 Blocks of Order 3:** *Equal block sums of order 3;*
- ii. **9 Blocks of Order 19:** *Equal magic square sums of order 19;*

2.32 Magic Squares of order 60

The magic sum of order 60 is given by

$$S_{60 \times 60} := \frac{60 \times (1 + 60^2)}{2} = 108030.$$

We can write, $60 := 2^2 \times 3 \times 5 = 2 \times 2 \times 3 \times 5$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 4, 5, 6, 10, 12, 15 and 20. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 108030 by 20, 15, 12, 10, 6, 5, 4 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{108030}{20} = 5401.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{108030}{15} = 7202 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (iii) $\frac{108030}{12} = 9002.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 5;
- (iv) $\frac{108030}{10} = 10803 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6;
- (v) $\frac{108030}{6} = 18005 \implies$ equal blocks of order 10;
- (vi) $\frac{108030}{5} = 21606 \implies$ equal blocks of order 12;
- (vii) $\frac{108030}{4} = 27007.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 15;
- (viii) $\frac{108030}{3} = 36010 \implies$ equal blocks of order 20.

Result 32. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 60 is given by*

- i. 400 Blocks of Order 3: Unequal magic squares of order 3;*
- ii. 225 Blocks of Order 4: In this case, pandigonal magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums results in a pandiagonal magic square of order 60;*
- iii. 144 Blocks of Order 5: In this case, pandigonal magic squares of order 5 with different magic sums results in a pandiagonal magic square of order 60.*
- iv. 100 Blocks of Order 6: Equal magic square sums of order 6;*
- v. 36 Blocks of Order 10: Equal magic square sums of order 10;*
- vi. 25 Blocks of Order 12: Equal magic square sums of order 12;*
- vii. 16 Blocks of Order 15: Unequal magic square sums of order 15;*
- viii. 9 Blocks of Order 20: Equal magic square sums of order 20;*

2.33 Magic Squares of order 63

The magic sum of order 63 is given by

$$S_{63 \times 63} := \frac{63 \times (1 + 63^2)}{2} = 125055.$$

We can write, $63 := 3^2 \times 7 = 3 \times 3 \times 7$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 7, 9 and 21. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 125055 by 21, 9, 7 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{125055}{21} = 5955 \implies$ equal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{125055}{9} = 13895 \implies$ equal blocks of order 7;
- (iii) $\frac{125055}{7} = 17865 \implies$ equal blocks of order 9;
- (iv) $\frac{125055}{3} = 41685 \implies$ equal blocks of order 21.

Result 33. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 63 is given by*

- i. 441 Blocks of Order 3: Equal block sums of order 3;*
- ii. 81 Blocks of Order 7: Equal magic square sums of order 7;*
- iii. 49 Blocks of Order 9: Equal magic square sums of order 9;*
- iv. 9 Blocks of Order 21: Equal magic square sums of order 21;*

2.34 Magic Squares of order 64

The magic sum of order 64 is given by

$$S_{64 \times 64} := \frac{64 \times (1 + 64^2)}{2} = 131104.$$

We can write, $64 := 2^6 = 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4, 8, and 16. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 131104 by 16, 8 and 4:

- (i) $\frac{131104}{16} = 8194 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (ii) $\frac{131104}{8} = 16388 \implies$ equal blocks of order 8;
- (iii) $\frac{131104}{4} = 32776 \implies$ equal blocks of order 16.

Result 34. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 64 is given by*

- i. 256 Blocks of Order 4: In this case, pandiagonal magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums results in a pandiagonal magic square of order 64;*
- ii. 84 Blocks of Order 8: Bimagic - Equal magic square sums of order 8;*
- iii. 16 Blocks of Order 16: Bimagic - Equal magic square sums of order 16;*

2.35 Magic Squares of order 65

The magic sum of order 65 is given by

$$S_{65 \times 65} := \frac{65 \times (1 + 65^2)}{2} = 137345.$$

We can write, $65 := 5 \times 13$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 5 and 13. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 137345 by 13 and 5:

- (i) $\frac{137345}{13} = 10565 \implies$ equal blocks of order 5;
- (ii) $\frac{137345}{5} = 27469 \implies$ equal blocks of order 13.

Result 35. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 65 is given by*

- i. **169 Blocks of Order 5:** *In this case, pandigonal magic squares of order 5 with equal magic sums results in a pandiagonal magic square of order 65;*
- ii. **25 Blocks of Order 13:** *In this case, pandigonal magic squares of order 13 with equal magic sums results in a pandiagonal magic square of order 65;*

2.36 Magic Squares of order 66

The magic sum of order 66 is given by

$$S_{66 \times 66} := \frac{66 \times (1 + 66^2)}{2} = 143781.$$

We can write, $66 := 2 \times 3 \times 11$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 6, 11 and 22. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 143781 by 22, 11, 6 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{143781}{22} = 6535.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{143781}{11} = 13071 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6;
- (iii) $\frac{143781}{6} = 23963.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 11;
- (iv) $\frac{143781}{3} = 47927 \implies$ equal blocks of order 22.

Result 36. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 66 is given by*

- i. **484 Blocks of Order 3:** *Unequal magic square sums of order 3;*
 - ii. **121 Blocks of Order 6:** *In this case, magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums results in a magic square of order 66.*
 - iii. **36 Blocks of Order 11:** *Unequal magic square sums of order 11;*
 - iv. **9 Blocks of Order 22:** *Equal magic square sums of order 22;*
- In this case, we don't have any pandiagonal magic square of order 66.*

2.37 Magic Squares of order 68

The magic sum of order 68 is given by

$$S_{68 \times 68} := \frac{68 \times (1 + 68^2)}{2} = 157250.$$

We can write, $68 := 2^2 \times 17 = 2 \times 2 \times 17$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4 and 17. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 157250 by 17 and 4:

- (i) $\frac{125055}{17} = 9250 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (ii) $\frac{125055}{4} = 39312.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 17.

Result 37. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 68 is given by*

- i. 289 Blocks of Order 4: Equal magic square sums of order 4;*
- ii. 16 Blocks of Order 17: Unequal magic square sums of order 17;*

2.38 Magic Squares of order 69

The magic sum of order 69 is given by

$$S_{69 \times 69} := \frac{69 \times (1 + 69^2)}{2} = 164289.$$

We can write, $69 := 3 \times 23$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3 and 23. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 164289 by 23 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{164289}{23} = 7143 \implies$ equal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{164289}{3} = 54763 \implies$ equal blocks of order 23.

Result 38. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 69 is given by*

- i. 529 Blocks of Order 3: Equal block sums of order 3;*
- ii. 9 Blocks of Order 23: Equal magic square sums of order 23;*

2.39 Magic Squares of order 70

The magic sum of order 70 is given by

$$S_{70 \times 70} := \frac{70 \times (1 + 70^2)}{2} = 171535.$$

We can write, $70 := 2 \times 5 \times 7$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 5, 7, 10 and 14. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 171535 by 14, 10, 7 and 5. See below:

- (i) $\frac{171535}{14} = 12252.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 5;
- (i) $\frac{171535}{10} = 17153.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 7;
- (ii) $\frac{171535}{7} = 24505 \implies$ equal blocks of order 10;
- (iii) $\frac{171535}{5} = 34307 \implies$ equal blocks of order 14.

Result 39. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 70 is given by*

- i. 196 Blocks of Order 5: Unequal magic square sums of order 5;*
- ii. 100 Blocks of Order 7: Unequal magic square sums of order 7;*
- iii. 49 Blocks of Order 10: Equal magic square sums of order 10;*
- iv. 25 Blocks of Order 14: Equal magic square sums of order 14;*

2.40 Magic Squares of order 72

The magic sum of order 72 is given by

$$S_{72 \times 72} := \frac{72 \times (1 + 72^2)}{2} = 186660.$$

We can write, $72 := 2^3 \times 3^2 = 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 3 \times 3$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 4, 6, 8, 9, 12, 18 and 24. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 186660 by 24, 18, 12, 9, 8, 6, 4 and 3. See below:

- (i) $\frac{186660}{24} = 7777.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{186660}{18} = 10370 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (iii) $\frac{186660}{12} = 15555 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6;
- (iv) $\frac{186660}{9} = 20740 \implies$ equal blocks of order 8;
- (v) $\frac{186660}{8} = 23332.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 9;
- (vi) $\frac{186660}{6} = 31110 \implies$ equal blocks of order 12;
- (vii) $\frac{186660}{4} = 46665 \implies$ equal blocks of order 18;
- (viii) $\frac{186660}{3} = 62220 \implies$ equal blocks of order 24.

Result 40. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 72 is given by*

- i. *576 Blocks of Order 3: Equal block sums of order 3;*
- ii. *324 Blocks of Order 4: Equal magic square sums of order 4;*
- iii. *144 Blocks of Order 6: In this case, magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums results in a magic square of order 66.*
- iv. *81 Blocks of Order 8: Bimagic - Equal magic square sums of order 8;*
- v. *64 Blocks of Order 9: Unequal magic square sums of order 9;*
- vi. *36 Blocks of Order 12: Equal magic square sums of order 12;*
- vii. *16 Blocks of Order 18: Equal magic square sums of order 18;*
- viii. *9 Blocks of Order 24: Equal magic square sums of order 24;*

2.41 Magic Squares of order 75

The magic sum of order 75 is given by

$$S_{75 \times 75} := \frac{75 \times (1 + 75^2)}{2} = 210975.$$

We can write, $75 := 3 \times 5^2 = 3 \times 5 \times 5$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 5, 15 and 25. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 210975 by 25, 15, 5 and 3. See below:

- (i) $\frac{210975}{25} = 8439 \implies$ equal blocks of order 3;
- (i) $\frac{210975}{15} = 14065 \implies$ equal blocks of order 5;
- (ii) $\frac{210975}{5} = 42195 \implies$ equal blocks of order 15;
- (iii) $\frac{210975}{3} = 70325 \implies$ equal blocks of order 25.

Result 41. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 75 is given by*

- i. 625 Blocks of Order 3: Equal block sums of order 3;*
- ii. 225 Blocks of Order 5: Equal magic square sums of order 5;*
- iii. 25 Blocks of Order 15: Equal magic square sums of order 15;*
- iv. 9 Blocks of Order 25: Equal magic square sums of order 25;*

2.42 Magic Squares of order 76

The magic sum of order 76 is given by

$$S_{76 \times 76} := \frac{76 \times (1 + 76^2)}{2} = 219526.$$

We can write, $76 := 2^2 \times 19 = 2 \times 2 \times 19$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4 and 19. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 219526 by 19 and 4. See below:

- (i) $\frac{219526}{19} = 11554 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (i) $\frac{219526}{4} = 54881.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 19.

Result 42. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 76 is given by*

- i. 361 Blocks of Order 4: Equal magic square sums of order 4;*
- ii. 16 Blocks of Order 19: Unequal magic square sums of order 19;*

2.43 Magic Squares of order 77

The magic sum of order 77 is given by

$$S_{77 \times 77} := \frac{77 \times (1 + 77^2)}{2} = 228305.$$

We can write, $77 := 7 \times 11$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 7 and 11. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 228305 by 11 and 7. See below:

- (i) $\frac{228305}{11} = 20755 \implies$ equal blocks of order 7;
- (ii) $\frac{228305}{7} = 32615 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 11.

Result 43. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 77 is given by*

- i. 121 Blocks of Order 7: Equal magic square sums of order 7;*
- ii. 7 Blocks of Order 11: Unequal magic square sums of order 11;*

2.44 Magic Squares of order 78

The magic sum of order 78 is given by

$$S_{78 \times 78} := \frac{78 \times (1 + 78^2)}{2} = 237315.$$

We can write, $78 := 2 \times 3 \times 13$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 6, 13 and 26. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 237315 by 26, 13, 6 and 3. See below:

- (i) $\frac{237315}{26} = 9127.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{237315}{13} = 18255 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6;
- (iii) $\frac{237315}{6} = 39552.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 13;
- (iv) $\frac{237315}{3} = 79105 \implies$ equal blocks of order 26.

Result 44. The block-wise construction of magic square of order 78 is given by

- i. 676 Blocks of Order 3: Unequal magic square sums of order 3;
 - ii. 169 Blocks of Order 6: Equal magic square sums of order 6;
 - iii. 36 Blocks of Order 13: Unequal magic square sums of order 13;
 - iv. 9 Blocks of Order 26: Equal magic square sums of order 26;
- In this case, we don't have any **pandiagonal** magic square of order 78.

2.45 Magic Squares of order 80

The magic sum of order 80 is given by

$$S_{80 \times 80} := \frac{80 \times (1 + 80^2)}{2} = 256040.$$

We can write, $72 := 2^4 \times 5 = 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 5$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4, 5, 8, 10, 16 and 32. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 256040 by 20, 16, 10, 8, 5 and 4:

- (i) $\frac{256040}{20} = 12802 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (ii) $\frac{256040}{16} = 16002.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 5;
- (iii) $\frac{256040}{10} = 25604 \implies$ equal blocks of order 8;
- (iv) $\frac{256040}{8} = 32005 \implies$ equal blocks of order 10;
- (v) $\frac{256040}{5} = 51208 \implies$ equal blocks of order 16;
- (vi) $\frac{256040}{4} = 64010 \implies$ equal blocks of order 20.

Result 45. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 80 is given by*

- i. 400 Blocks of Order 4: Equal magic square sums of order 4;*
- ii. 256 Blocks of Order 5: Unequal magic square sums of order 5;*
- iii. 100 Blocks of Order 8: Bimagic - Equal magic square sums of order 8;*
- iv. 80 Blocks of Order 10: Equal magic square sums of order 10;*
- v. 25 Blocks of Order 16: Bimagic - Equal magic square sums of order 16;*
- vi. 16 Blocks of Order 20: Equal magic square sums of order 20;*

2.46 Magic Squares of order 81

The magic sum of order 81 is given by

$$S_{81 \times 81} := \frac{81 \times (1 + 81^2)}{2} = 265761.$$

We can write, $81 := 3^4 = 3 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 9 and 27. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 265761 by 27, 9 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{265761}{27} = 9843 \implies$ equal blocks of order 3;
- (i) $\frac{265761}{9} = 29529 \implies$ equal blocks of order 9;
- (i) $\frac{265761}{3} = 88587 \implies$ equal blocks of order 27;

Result 46. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 81 is given by*

- i. 729 Blocks of Order 3: Equal block sums of order 3;*
- ii. 81 Blocks of Order 9: Bimagic - Equal magic square sums of order 9;*
- iii. 9 Blocks of Order 27: Equal magic square sums of order 27;*

2.47 Magic Squares of order 84

The magic sum of order 84 is given by

$$S_{84 \times 84} := \frac{84 \times (1 + 84^2)}{2} = 296394.$$

We can write, $84 := 2^2 \times 3 \times 7 = 2 \times 2 \times 3 \times 7$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 4, 6, 7, 12, 14, 21 and 28. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 296394 by 28, 21, 14, 12, 7, 6, 4 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{296394}{28} = 10585.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{296394}{21} = 14114 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (iii) $\frac{296394}{14} = 21171 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6;
- (iv) $\frac{296394}{12} = 24699.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 7;
- (v) $\frac{296394}{7} = 42342 \implies$ equal blocks of order 12;
- (vi) $\frac{296394}{6} = 49399 \implies$ equal blocks of order 14;
- (vii) $\frac{296394}{4} = 74098.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 21;
- (viii) $\frac{296394}{3} = 98798 \implies$ equal blocks of order 28.

Result 47. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 84 is given by*

- i. 784 Blocks of Order 3: Unequal magic square sums of order 3;*
- ii. 441 Blocks of Order 4: Equal magic square sums of order 4;*
- iii. 196 Blocks of Order 6: Equal magic square sums of order 6;*
- iv. 144 Blocks of Order 7: Unequal magic square sums of order 7;*
- v. 49 Blocks of Order 12: Equal magic square sums of order 12;*
- vi. 36 Blocks of Order 14: Equal magic square sums of order 14;*
- vii. 16 Blocks of Order 21: Unequal magic square sums of order 21;*
- viii. 9 Blocks of Order 28: Equal magic square sums of order 28;*

2.48 Magic Squares of order 85

The magic sum of order 85 is given by

$$S_{85 \times 85} := \frac{85 \times (1 + 85^2)}{2} = 307105.$$

We can write, $85 := 5 \times 17$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 5 and 17. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 307105 by 17 and 5:

- (i) $\frac{307105}{17} = 18065 \implies$ equal blocks of order 5;
- (ii) $\frac{307105}{5} = 61421 \implies$ equal blocks of order 17.

Result 48. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 85 is given by*

- i. 289 Blocks of Order 5: Equal magic square sums of order 5;*
- ii. 25 Blocks of Order 17: Equal magic square sums of order 17;*

2.49 Magic Squares of order 87

The magic sum of order 87 is given by

$$S_{87 \times 87} := \frac{87 \times (1 + 87^2)}{2} = 329295.$$

We can write, $87 := 3 \times 29$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3 and 29. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 329295 by 29 and 3:

$$(i) \quad \frac{329295}{29} = 11355 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 3;}$$

$$(ii) \quad \frac{329295}{3} = 109765 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 29.}$$

Result 49. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 87 is given by*

- i. 841 Blocks of Order 3: Equal block sums of order 3;*
- ii. 9 Blocks of Order 29: Equal magic square sums of order 29;*

2.50 Magic Squares of order 88

The magic sum of order 88 is given by

$$S_{88 \times 88} := \frac{88 \times (1 + 88^2)}{2} = 340780.$$

We can write, $88 := 2^3 \times 11 = 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 11$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4, 8, 11 and 22. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 340780 by 22, 11, 8 and 4:

$$(i) \quad \frac{329295}{22} = 15490 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 4;}$$

$$(ii) \quad \frac{329295}{11} = 30980 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 8;}$$

$$(iii) \quad \frac{329295}{8} = 42597.5 \implies \text{unequal blocks of order 11;}$$

$$(iv) \quad \frac{329295}{4} = 85195 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 22.}$$

Result 50. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 88 is given by*

- i. 484 Blocks of Order 4: Equal magic square sums of order 4;*
- ii. 121 Blocks of Order 8: Bimagic - Equal magic square sums of order 8;*
- iii. 64 Blocks of Order 11: Equal magic square sums of order 11;*
- iv. 16 Blocks of Order 22: Equal magic square sums of order 22;*

2.51 Magic Squares of order 90

The magic sum of order 90 is given by

$$S_{90 \times 90} := \frac{90 \times (1 + 90^2)}{2} = 364545.$$

We can write, $88 := 2 \times 3^2 \times 5 = 2 \times 3 \times 3 \times 5$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 5, 6, 9, 10, 15, 18 and 30. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 364545 by 30, 18, 15, 10, 9, 6, 5 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{329295}{30} = 12151.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{329295}{18} = 20252.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 5;
- (iii) $\frac{329295}{15} = 24303 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6;
- (iv) $\frac{329295}{10} = 36454.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 9;
- (v) $\frac{329295}{9} = 40505 \implies$ equal blocks of order 10;
- (vi) $\frac{329295}{6} = 60757.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 15;
- (vii) $\frac{329295}{5} = 72909 \implies$ equal blocks of order 18;
- (viii) $\frac{329295}{3} = 121515 \implies$ equal blocks of order 30.

Result 51. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 90 is given by*

- i. 900 Blocks of Order 3: Unequal magic square sums of order 3;*
- ii. 324 Blocks of Order 5: Unequal magic square sums of order 5;*
- iii. 225 Blocks of Order 6: Equal magic square sums of order 6;*
- iv. 100 Blocks of Order 9: Unequal magic square sums of order 9;*
- v. 81 Blocks of Order 10: Equal magic square sums of order 10;*
- vi. 36 Blocks of Order 15: Unequal magic square sums of order 15;*
- vii. 25 Blocks of Order 18: Equal magic square sums of order 18;*
- viii. 9 Blocks of Order 30: Equal magic square sums of order 30;*

In this case, we don't have any pandiagonal magic square of order 90.

2.52 Magic Squares of order 91

The magic sum of order 91 is given by

$$S_{91 \times 91} := \frac{91 \times (1 + 91^2)}{2} = 376831.$$

We can write, $91 := 7 \times 13$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 7 and 13. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 376831 by 13 and 7:

$$(i) \quad \frac{376831}{13} = 28987 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 7;}$$
$$(ii) \quad \frac{376831}{7} = 53833 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 13.}$$

Result 52. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 91 is given by*

- i. 169 Blocks of Order 7: Equal magic square sums of order 7;*
- ii. 49 Blocks of Order 13: Equal magic square sums of order 13;*

2.53 Magic Squares of order 92

The magic sum of order 92 is given by

$$S_{92 \times 92} := \frac{92 \times (1 + 92^2)}{2} = 389390.$$

We can write, $92 := 2^2 \times 23 = 2 \times 2 \times 23$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4 and 23. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 389390 by 23 and 4:

$$(i) \quad \frac{389390}{23} = 16930 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 4;}$$
$$(ii) \quad \frac{389390}{4} = 97347.5 \implies \text{unequal blocks of order 23.}$$

Result 53. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 92 is given by*

- i. 529 Blocks of Order 4: Equal magic square sums of order 4;*
- ii. 16 Blocks of Order 23: Unequal magic square sums of order 23;*

2.54 Magic Squares of order 93

The magic sum of order 93 is given by

$$S_{93 \times 93} := \frac{93 \times (1 + 93^2)}{2} = 402225.$$

We can write, $93 := 3 \times 31$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3 and 31. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 402225 by 31 and 3:

$$(i) \quad \frac{402225}{31} = 12975 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 3;}$$
$$(ii) \quad \frac{402225}{3} = 134075 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 31.}$$

Result 54. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 93 is given by*

- i. 961 Blocks of Order 3: Equal block sums of order 3;*
- ii. 9 Blocks of Order 31: Equal magic square sums of order 31;*

2.55 Magic Squares of order 95

The magic sum of order 95 is given by

$$S_{95 \times 95} := \frac{95 \times (1 + 95^2)}{2} = 428735.$$

We can write, $95 := 5 \times 19$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 5 and 19. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 428735 by 19 and 5:

$$(i) \quad \frac{428735}{19} = 22565 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 5;}$$
$$(ii) \quad \frac{428735}{5} = 85747 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 19.}$$

Result 55. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 95 is given by*

- i. 361 Blocks of Order 5: Equal magic square sums of order 5;*
- ii. 25 Blocks of Order 19: Equal magic square sums of order 19;*

2.56 Magic Squares of order 96

The magic sum of order 96 is given by

$$S_{96 \times 96} := \frac{96 \times (1 + 96^2)}{2} = 442416.$$

We can write, $96 := 2^5 \times 3 = 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 2 \times 3$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 4, 6, 8, 12, 16, 24 and 32. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 442416 by 32, 24, 16, 12, 8, 6, 4 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{442416}{32} = 13825.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{442416}{24} = 18434 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (iii) $\frac{442416}{16} = 27651 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6;
- (iv) $\frac{442416}{12} = 36868 \implies$ equal blocks of order 8;
- (v) $\frac{442416}{8} = 55302 \implies$ equal blocks of order 12;
- (vi) $\frac{442416}{6} = 73736 \implies$ equal blocks of order 16;
- (vii) $\frac{442416}{4} = 110604 \implies$ equal blocks of order 24;
- (viii) $\frac{442416}{3} = 147472 \implies$ equal blocks of order 32.

Result 56. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 96 is given by*

- i. 1024 Blocks of Order 3: Unequal magic square sums of order 3;*
- ii. 576 Blocks of Order 4: Equal magic square sums of order 4;*
- iii. 256 Blocks of Order 6: Equal magic square sums of order 6;*
- iv. 144 Blocks of Order 8: Bimagic - Equal magic square sums of order 8;*
- v. 64 Blocks of Order 12: Equal magic square sums of order 12;*
- vi. 36 Blocks of Order 16: Equal magic square sums of order 16;*
- vii. 16 Blocks of Order 24: Equal magic square sums of order 24;*
- viii. 9 Blocks of Order 32: Equal magic square sums of order 32;*

2.57 Magic Squares of order 98

The magic sum of order 98 is given by

$$S_{98 \times 98} := \frac{98 \times (1 + 98^2)}{2} = 470645$$

We can write, $98 := 2 \times 7^2 = 2 \times 7 \times 7$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 7 and 14. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 470645 by 14 and 7:

$$(i) \quad \frac{470645}{14} = 33617.5 \implies \text{unequal blocks of order 7;}$$
$$(ii) \quad \frac{470645}{7} = 67235 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 14.}$$

Result 57. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 98 is given by*

- i. 196 Blocks of Order 7: Unequal magic square sums of order 7;*
- ii. 49 Blocks of Order 14: Equal magic square sums of order 14;*

2.58 Magic Squares of order 99

The magic sum of order 99 is given by

$$S_{99 \times 99} := \frac{99 \times (1 + 99^2)}{2} = 485199.$$

We can write, $99 := 3^2 \times 11 = 3 \times 3 \times 11$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 9, 11 and 33. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 485199 by 33, 11, 9 and 3:

$$(i) \quad \frac{485199}{33} = 14703 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 3;}$$
$$(ii) \quad \frac{485199}{11} = 44109 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 9;}$$
$$(iii) \quad \frac{485199}{9} = 53911 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 11;}$$
$$(iv) \quad \frac{485199}{3} = 161733 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 33.}$$

Result 58. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 99 is given by*

- i. 1089 Blocks of Order 3: Equal block sums of order 3;*
- ii. 121 Blocks of Order 9: Equal magic square sums of order 9;*
- iii. 81 Blocks of Order 11: Equal magic square sums of order 11;*
- iv. 9 Blocks of Order 33: Equal magic square sums of order 33;*

2.59 Magic Squares of order 100

The magic sum of order 100 is given by

$$S_{100 \times 100} := \frac{100 \times (1 + 100^2)}{2} = 500050.$$

We can write, $100 := 2^2 \times 5^2 = 2 \times 2 \times 5 \times 5$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4, 5, 10, 20 and 25. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 500050 by 25, 20, 10, 5 and 4:

- (i) $\frac{500050}{25} = 20002 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (ii) $\frac{500050}{20} = 25002.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 5;
- (iii) $\frac{500050}{10} = 50005 \implies$ equal blocks of order 10;
- (iv) $\frac{500050}{5} = 100010 \implies$ equal blocks of order 20;
- (v) $\frac{500050}{4} = 125012.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 25.

Result 59. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 100 is given by*

- i. 625 Blocks of Order 4: Equal magic square sums of order 4;*
- ii. 400 Blocks of Order 5: Equal magic square sums of order 5;*
- iii. 100 Blocks of Order 10: Equal magic square sums of order 10;*
- iv. 25 Blocks of Order 20: Equal magic square sums of order 20;*
- v. 16 Blocks of Order 25: Unequal magic square sums of order 25;*

2.60 Magic Squares of order 102

The magic sum of order 102 is given by

$$S_{102 \times 102} := \frac{102 \times (1 + 102^2)}{2} = 530655.$$

We can write, $102 := 2 \times 3 \times 17$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 6, 17 and 34. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 530655 by 34, 17, 6 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{530655}{34} = 15607.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{530655}{17} = 31215 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6;
- (iii) $\frac{530655}{6} = 88442.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 17;
- (iv) $\frac{530655}{3} = 176885 \implies$ equal blocks of order 34.

Result 60. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 102 is given by*

- i. 1156 Blocks of Order 3: Unequal magic square sums of order 3;*
- ii. 289 Blocks of Order 6: Equal magic square sums of order 6;*
- iii. 36 Blocks of Order 17: Unequal magic square sums of order 17;*
- iv. 9 Blocks of Order 34: Equal magic square sums of order 34;*

*In this case, we don't have any **pandiagonal** magic square of order 102.*

2.61 Magic Squares of order 104

The magic sum of order 104 is given by

$$S_{104 \times 104} := \frac{104 \times (1 + 104^2)}{2} = 562484.$$

We can write, $99 := 2^3 \times 13 = 2 \times 2 \times 2$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 4, 8, 13 and 26. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 562484 by 26, 13, 8 and 4:

- (i) $\frac{562484}{26} = 21634 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (ii) $\frac{562484}{13} = 43268 \implies$ equal blocks of order 8;
- (iii) $\frac{562484}{8} = 70310.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 13;
- (iv) $\frac{562484}{4} = 140621 \implies$ equal blocks of order 26.

Result 61. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 104 is given by*

- i. 676 Blocks of Order 4: Equal magic square sums of order 4;*
- ii. 169 Blocks of Order 8: Bimagic - Equal magic square sums of order 8;*
- iii. 64 Blocks of Order 13: Unequal magic square sums of order 13;*
- iv. 16 Blocks of Order 26: Equal magic square sums of order 26;*

2.62 Magic Squares of order 105

The magic sum of order 105 is given by

$$S_{105 \times 105} := \frac{105 \times (1 + 105^2)}{2} = 578865.$$

We can write, $105 := 3 \times 5 \times 7$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 5, 7, 15, 21 and 35. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 578865 by 35, 21, 15, 7, 5 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{578865}{35} = 16539 \implies$ equal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{578865}{21} = 27565 \implies$ equal blocks of order 5;
- (iii) $\frac{578865}{15} = 38591 \implies$ equal blocks of order 7;
- (iv) $\frac{578865}{7} = 82695 \implies$ equal blocks of order 15;
- (v) $\frac{578865}{5} = 115773 \implies$ equal blocks of order 21;
- (vi) $\frac{578865}{3} = 192955 \implies$ equal blocks of order 35.

Result 62. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 105 is given by*

- i. 1225 Blocks of Order 3: Equal block sums of order 3;*
- ii. 441 Blocks of Order 5: Equal magic square sums of order 5;*
- iii. 225 Blocks of Order 7: Equal magic square sums of order 7;*
- iv. 49 Blocks of Order 15: Equal magic square sums of order 15;*
- v. 25 Blocks of Order 21: Equal magic square sums of order 21;*
- vi. 3 Blocks of Order 35: Equal magic square sums of order 35;*

2.63 Magic Squares of order 108

The magic sum of order 108 is given by

$$S_{108 \times 108} := \frac{108 \times (1 + 108^2)}{2} = 629910.$$

We can write, $108 := 2^2 \times 3^3 = 2 \times 2 \times 3 \times 3 \times 3$. This gives the possibilities of blocks of orders 3, 4, 6, 9, 12, 18, 27 and 36. Let's see the divisions of magic square sum 629910 by 36, 27, 18, 12, 9, 6, 4 and 3:

- (i) $\frac{629910}{36} = 17497.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 3;
- (ii) $\frac{629910}{27} = 23330 \implies$ equal blocks of order 4;
- (iii) $\frac{629910}{18} = 34995 \implies$ equal blocks of order 6;
- (iv) $\frac{629910}{12} = 52492.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 9;
- (v) $\frac{629910}{9} = 69990 \implies$ equal blocks of order 12;
- (vi) $\frac{629910}{6} = 104985 \implies$ equal blocks of order 18;
- (vii) $\frac{629910}{4} = 157477.5 \implies$ unequal blocks of order 27
- (viii) $\frac{629910}{3} = 209970 \implies$ equal blocks of order 36.

Result 63. *The block-wise construction of magic square of order 108 is given by*

- i. 1296 Blocks of Order 3: Unequal magic square sums of order 3;*
- ii. 729 Blocks of Order 4: Equal magic square sums of order 4;*
- iii. 324 Blocks of Order 6: Equal magic square sums of order 6;*
- iv. 144 Blocks of Order 9: Unequal magic square sums of order 9;*
- v. 81 Blocks of Order 12: Equal magic square sums of order 12;*
- vi. 36 Blocks of Order 18: Equal magic square sums of order 18;*
- vii. 16 Blocks of Order 27: Unequal magic square sums of order 27;*
- viii. 9 Blocks of Order 36: Equal magic square sums of order 36;*

Remark 2.2. *i. The block-wise construction of magic squares up to order 45 can be seen in author's work [22, 23, 24, 28, 31]. The other magic squares specified above are under study;*

*ii. In orders studied above, it is always possible to have at least one of the possibility being a **pandiagonal** magic square, except the orders 6, 18, 30, etc.*

3 Author's Contributions to Magic Squares

The **item-wise** author's work on magic squares is as follows:

- i. Digital Numbers Magic Squares - [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12];*
- ii. Block-Wise Construction of Bimagic Squares - [13];*
- iii. Connections with Genetic Tables and Shannon's entropy - [14];*
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